

ADVANTAGES OF USING AND DEVELOPING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN TOURISM

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Annotatsiya: So'nggi bir necha yil ichida Blokcheyn (Blockchain) texnologiyasi iqtisodiyotning ko'plab sohalarida katta qiziqish uyg'otdi. Buning asosiy sababi esa blokcheyn algoritmlaridan foydalanish oshkoralik va xavfsizlik masalalarini tubdan yaxshilashi tufaylidir.

Kalit so'zlar: blokcheyn, turizm, token, kriptovalyuta, biometrik.

Аннотация: За последние несколько лет технология Блокчейн (Blockchain) вызвала большой интерес во многих секторах экономики. Основная причина этого заключается в том, что использование алгоритмов блокчейна значительно улучшает прозрачность и безопасность.

Ключивые слова: блокчейн, туризм, токен, криптовалюта, биометрический.

Annotation: Over the past few years, Blockchain technology has generated a great deal of interest in many sectors of the economy. The main reason for this is that the use of blockchain algorithms has radically improved transparency and security.

Keywords: blockchain, tourism, token, crypto-currency, biometric.

Uzbekistan is undergoing government-sponsored tourism development reforms. The purpose of promoting these reforms is, of course, to increase the welfare of the population, to help the image of our country to find its place in the world tourism market. In addition, it is aimed at ensuring the stability of the country's economy and thereby increasing the share of tourism in the country's GDP.

Today, blockchain is one of the most advanced technologies, penetrating into all aspects of the world economy. Tourism is no exception. Blockchain helps to get rid of monopoly in the market, as a result of which the tourist is able to travel independently based on the best recommendations, choosing offers with cheap and convenient, the highest quality and the biggest discounts. It can answer the tourist's questions about hotels, restaurants, discounts, shopping, attractions and entertainment.

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The creation of a tourist blockchain platform will pave the way for a smart tourism system, freeing the tourism industry from costly intermediaries, allowing more, cheaper and more convenient travel. According to experts, one of the most promising areas for the use of blockchain technology in tourism is the tokenization of hotel services. Everyone who is

abroad is at risk of being scammed by private currency exchanges and misunderstandings in the use of payment systems and cards when buying local currency. To address this, hotels (especially large chain hotels) can issue their own internal cryptocurrencies and use them within additional services, souvenirs, excursions. In general, the tokenization of hotel services will be more beneficial than usual. Hotels can raise additional funds by issuing tokens. Tourists will be able to buy tokens knowing the exchange rate in advance and sell their surplus tokens safely.

Another problem in tourism is the insurance industry. Insurance is another promising area of blockchain technology. Currently, the process of compensating for a delayed or canceled flight is associated with many problems, and travelers lose time, money and nerves. There may be smart contracts to help in this situation, the specificity of which allows the affected tourists to automatically pay insurance premiums, as well as book new tickets. A smart contract can be made so that the money from the tourist is immediately transferred to certain agents at the time of payment. Thus, a system of decentralized and transparent operations will be created. In blockchain, the service provider protects the interests of the provider and the consumer. This requirement guarantees the rights of tourists if it is specified in the smart contract with the hotel, and protects the hotel from unreasonable demands of tourists. If there is any deviation from the terms of the contract, the system will automatically penalize the offender and compensate the victim. The main task of the blockchain is to protect its economic interests, so blockchain-based contracts prevent various manipulations.

Another important positive aspect of blockchain technology in tourism is the ability to reduce costs and lower the cost of tourism services. All available large aggregators operate for a percentage, i.e., a commission is charged from the supplier or consumer, and some receive a commission from both parties. Blockchain-based travel smart platform does not require commission fees.

Blockchain technology eliminates monopolies in the tourism business and significantly improves the competitive environment. It allows you to perform all transactions between buyer and seller immediately, which is very cheap and efficient.

Conclusion.

Increasing of the efficiency of the use of blockchain technologies in our country, it is necessary to work not only on the use of one network, but also on new applications. For example, the development of programs to attract foreign tourists to promote our country in the virtual world of the Internet. At the same time, it is necessary to attract tourists to the developed shows in the virtual world, to increase the attractiveness for tourists with virtual shows. The virtual world has to be so perfectly prepared that everyone who watches it has to be able to take their minds out of the real world. The role of advertising in the program is of great importance in attracting tourists. But advertising should not be exaggerated, but in a way that makes everything interesting.

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